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HOMOLOGY MODELING AND MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY OF *MYCOBACTERIUM TUBERCULOSIS* UREASE

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Introduction

Mycobacterium tuberculosis, the causative agent of tuberculosis, infects approximately one third of the world's population and kills almost 2 million people every year [1]. Although it is frequently proposed that vaccination is the most effective way to combat tuberculosis, numerous attempts to develop more efficacious vaccines than available ones have failed [2]. Thus, new anti-tuberculosis drugs are urgently needed. One of the potential targets for chemotherapeutic intervention in tuberculosis is *M. tuberculosis* urease (MTU).

Urease, a nickel-containing enzyme (urea amidohydrolase, EC 3.5.1.5) [3-6], is produced by

various bacteria [7-17], fungi [8, 18], and plants [7, 8, 19-21]. Within past two decades bacterial ureases have gained much attention in research field as a virulence factor in human and animal infections [7, 8, 17, 22-24], and, correspondingly, as an attractive target for designing new safe and efficient enzyme inhibitors aimed to combat infectious diseases stipulated by urease activity [25-34]. A prerequisite for designing such inhibitors is an understanding of urease's three-dimensional (3D) structure organization.

Plant and fungal ureases are homo-oligomeric proteins, while bacterial ureases are multimers of three-subunits (except *Helicobacter pylori* which comprises two-subunits). Despite these differences, bacterial and plant ureases are homologous, and have a similar three-dimensional structure (fig. 1) and conservative catalytic mechanism [6, 7, 35, 36]. Three sub-units of bacterial ureases, UreC (α -chain), UreB (β -chain), and UreA (γ -chain), form a T-shaped heterotrimer $\alpha\beta\gamma$ (fig. 1). Three $\alpha\beta\gamma$ heterotrimers form quaternary complex $(\alpha\beta\gamma)_3$, homotrimer of heterotrimers. Active center is located in α -domain and contains two atoms of nickel coordinated by carboxylated lysine, aspartic acid and histidine

Fig. 1. – Sub-unit organization and X-ray structure of bacterial and plant ureases. A – characteristic bacterial urease, *Klebsiella aerogenes* urease, consisting of three sub-units: α (cyan), β (gold) and γ (lilac) (PDB code 2KAU). B – *Helicobacter pylori* urease consisting of two sub-units: α (cyan) and β (lilac) (PDB code 1E9Z). C – characteristic eukariotic urease, jack bean urease, represented by a single α (cyan) unit (PDB code 1E9Z).

residues. Active site is capped by a flap that controls substrate ingress to and product egress from the dinickel center. Amongst bacterial ureases, only X-ray structures of the enzymes from *Helicobacter pylori*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, and *Sporosarcina pasteurii* (formerly known as *Bacillus pasteurii*) have been determined till now [37-40]. Three-dimensional structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease is unknown. X-ray structure has been determined only for its γ sub-unit, which unlike α and β sub-units has no known enzymatic functions and supposed to serve as a scaffold for the urease quaternary complex $(\alpha\beta\gamma)_3$ [41]. When experimental three-dimensional structure of a protein is not known, homology modeling, the most commonly used computational structure prediction method, is the technique of choice [42-44]. This paper aimed to build a 3D-structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease by homology modeling and to study its stability by molecular dynamics simulations.

Materials and methods

Homology modeling. The target amino acid sequence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv urease was retrieved from GenBank at NCBI: α -chain (UreC), 100 amino acid residues (Accession AAC3707.01, GJ:886331); β -chain (UreB), 104 amino acid residues (Accession AAC37006.1, GJ:886330), and γ -chain (UreA), 577 amino acid residues (Accession AAC37005.1, GJ:886329) [45]. Potential modeling templates were identified by running PSI-BLAST [46, 47] to extract a position-specific scoring matrix from UniRef90 and then searching the PDB [48] for a match with the target sequence. The templates were ranked based on the alignment score and the structural quality according to WHAT_CHECK [49] obtained from the PDBFinder2 database [50]. Amongst the top-scoring templates, five high-resolution X-ray structures were selected for *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Sporosarcina pasteurii*, and *Enterobacter aerogenes* bacterial ureases with three-subunit composition: 2KAU, 5G4H, 4UBP, 4CEU, and 4EPB. The template's amino acid sequence identity with the target was within 56.9% - 59.1%. For each template five stochastic alignments were created [51] using SSALIGN scoring matrices [52]. Then for each alignment, a three-dimensional model was built using loop conformation extracted from the PDB [53] and the SCRWL side-chain placement algorithm [54].

Hydrogen bonding network was optimized [55]. Each model was energy minimized with explicit water molecules using Yasara2 force field [56], and the models were ranked by quality Z-score. The best scoring model was further refined by running a 500 ps molecular dynamics simulation using Yasara2 force field. During the simulation, snapshots were saved every 25 ps and rated according to the quality Z-score. The model with highest quality score was chosen as a final homology model of 3D structure for *M. tuberculosis* urease.

Homology model building, refining, validation, molecular dynamics simulations, and analysis as well as the result presentation by using molecular graphics were done by molecular modeling program YASARA Structure [55-61]. Additionally, the final model was validated by using QMEAN [62-64], PDBsum [65-70], and PISA [71] servers.

Molecular dynamics. MTU trimer $\alpha\beta\gamma$ was placed in a cubic periodic cell filled with TIP3P water molecules. The simulation cell was 1 nm larger than the trimer complex along all three axes. Na^+ and Cl^- counterions were added to neutralize the system and to reach ion mass fraction 0.9% NaCl [59]. The system was energy-minimized using AMBER14 force field [72] with a 1.05 nm force cutoff for dispersion interactions. To treat longrange electrostatic interactions the Particle Mesh Ewald algorithm [73] was used. After a short steepest descent minimization, the procedure continued by simulated annealing minimization. The molecular dynamics simulations were run in NPT ensemble at 300 K and pH 7.4 using a multiple timestep of 2.5 fs for intra-molecular and 5 fs for inter-molecular forces [61]. Trajectory was computed for 60 ns

Results and discussion

Homology model of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* urease. Homology model of MTU is a nonamer (homotrimer of heterotrimers, $(\alpha\beta\gamma)_3$) consisting of 2349 residues (fig. 2). To build MTU model, five high-resolution X-ray structures of bacterial ureases with three-subunit composition (2KAU, 5G4H, 4UBP, 4CEU, and 4EPB) have been selected as templates. For each template five stochastic alignments were created and for each alignment, a three-dimensional model was built. Then, each model was energy minimized and the models were ranked by quality Z-score. A quality Z-score estimates the quality of a model in relation to experimental high-resolution X-ray structures. Z-score is normalized to mean 0

Fig. 2 – 3D model of *M. tuberculosis* urease. A – homotrimer of heterotrimers ($\alpha\beta\gamma$)₃. The homotrimers are differently colored. B – sub-unit structure of the homotrimer of heterotrimers ($\alpha\beta\gamma$)₃. In each heterotrimer, α , β and γ sub-units are differently colored.

and standard deviation 1 and indicates how many standard deviations the model differs from values for experimental structures. Z-scores form the basis of most structure validation tools. The Yasara's quality Z-score based on knowledge-based dihedral angle and packing potentials is weighted sum of 'Dihedrals', 'Packing1D' and 'Packing3D' contributions [56]. The MTU model with highest quality estimation amongst 25 potential models was selected. To further improve structure quality the model was refined by short molecular dynamics simulation that resulted in 20 snapshots which were rated

according to their energy and the quality Z-score. The best scoring model having minimum energy was chosen as a final homology model of 3D structure for *M. tuberculosis*. Fig. 3 shows MTU heterotrimer $\alpha\beta\gamma$ colored according to per-residue Z-score values.

The model of MTU was also validated by using PDBsum and QMEAN servers. Ramachandran plots for MTU heterotrimer and homotrimer of heterotrimers are shown in fig. 4.

Fig. 3 – MTU heterotrimer $\alpha\beta\gamma$ colored according to per-residue Z-score values. Colors range from yellow (bad/incorrect) to blue (perfect/correct).

In heterotrimer (fig. 4A), 90.2%, 8.7%, 0.9%, and 0.2% of total residues are present in the most favored, additional allowed, generously allowed, and disallowed regions, respectively. In homotrimer of heterotrimers

(fig. 4B), 90.1%, 8.5%, 1.0%, and 0.4% of total residues are present, respectively, in the most favored, additional allowed, generously allowed, and disallowed regions.

QMEAN Z-score estimates an absolute quality of a protein structure by relating the model's structural

features to experimental structures of similar size. The QMEAN's scoring function is a weighted linear combination of four statistical potential terms (torsion, pairwise C_{β} , all-atom interactions and solvation) and two additional terms describing the agreement of the predicted and observed secondary structure, and solvent

accessibility [62-63]. Fig. 5 shows QMEAN score of MTU model compared to the experimental structures of similar size from PDB. The MTU (query model) score is colored in red. Fig. 6 represents density plot of all

Fig. 4. - Ramachandran plots for MTU heterotrimer (A) and homotrimer of heterotrimers (B). (Generated from PDBsum server).

Fig. 5 – QMEAN score of MTU compared to the experimental structures of similar size from the PDB. (Generated from QMEAN server.)

reference models used in the Z-score calculation as well as the location of MTU model (marked in red). Thus, above structure validations confirm good quality of our homology model of *M. tuberculosis* urease.

In *M. tuberculosis* urease heterotrimer, sub-units α , β , and γ tightly interact with each other at a surface of approximately 3000 Å². Secondary structure of sub-units γ , β , and α is shown in fig. 7A, B and C, respectively. Topological scheme of mutual arrangement of the secondary structure elements in these sub-units is presented in figs. 8 and 9.

Sub-unit α contains the enzyme active site with two Ni atoms coordinated by amino acid residues His347, His349, carbamylated Lys430*, His459, His485, Asp 573, Gly490 (fig. 10). Helix-turn-helix motif (residues 524-545) forms a mobile flap that covers the active site (fig. 11A). The flap of bacterial ureases have been shown to exist in closed, open and wide-open conformations, respectively closing, opening and wide-opening access to the active site, and thus playing a key role in the control of urease activity [74-76]. In our model, the flap is in closed conformation impeding access to the enzyme active site (fig. 11B).

Molecular dynamics study of *M. tuberculosis* urease. The structural stability of our homology model was checked by molecular dynamics simulation of MTU in explicit water at 300 K and pH 7.4. During the simulation, root mean square deviations of C α atoms (RMSD C α) and root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) of amino acid residues of MTU were monitored for 60 ns. As can be seen from fig.12, after equilibration

Fig. 6 – Density plot of all reference models used in the Z-score calculation. The location of MTU model (“query model”) with regard to the background distribution is marked in red. The number of reference models used in the calculation is shown under the plot. (Generated from QMEAN server.)

(beyond 20 ns) RMSD C α values change insignificantly evidencing that MTU global structure is quite stable.

Analysis of RMSF values for individual amino acid residues of MTU, especially ones for its α sub-unit, reveals their different mobility (fig. 13). The highest fluctuations are observed in the regions covering residues Gly598-Asp612 and Asn520-Arg549. Residues of the first region form a loop situated at the periphery of the enzyme and supposed to be involved in intermolecular interactions between the apoenzyme and the accessory proteins that form the supercomplex that is necessary for the incorporation of the Ni ions at the active site and for the consequent urease activation [35, 74-77]. The other region corresponds to helix-turn-helix motif which forms a flap that covers the active site and modulates the enzyme activity [78-80], and thus is of the most interest for our analysis. In our model, the flap was in closed conformation.

To study the possible movement of this loop in relation to the active center (i.e. its potential for opening) there was monitored the distance between loop center and dinickel center for 60 ns. As can be seen from fig. 14, the distance between the loop and Ni atoms fluctuates in time around its average value 15.7 Å

Fig. 7 – Secondary structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease. A, B and C represent γ , β and α subunits, correspondingly. (Generated from PDBsum server).

Fig. 8 – The topology diagram of the secondary structure elements in γ (left) and β (right) sub-units of *M. tuberculosis* urease. The large pink arrows are beta strands, the red cylinders are alpha-helices. The small blue arrows indicate the directionality of the protein chain. The numbers within the secondary structural elements correspond to the first and the last residue numbers. (Generated from PDBsum server.)

Fig. 9 –The topology diagram of mutual arrangement of the secondary structure elements in *M. tuberculosis* urease α sub-unit. The large pink arrows denote beta strands, the red cylinders denote alpha-helices. The small blue arrows indicate the directionality of the protein chain. The numbers within the secondary structural elements correspond to the first and the last residue numbers. (Generated from PDBsum server.)

Fig. 10 - Nickel-protein interactions in the active site. Nickels, carbons, oxygens, and nitrogens are colored in green, black, red, and blue, respectively. Unk430 denotes carbamylated Lys430*. (Generated from PDBsum server).

Fig. 11 – The flap (helix–turn–helix motif) covering the active-site cleft. A – homotrimer of heterotrimers. B – Enlarged active site region of α sub-unit. Helices and turns are colored in blue and red, Ni atoms and the active-site residues are shown in green and pink, correspondingly.

Fig. 12 – Root mean square deviations of C α atoms (RMSD C α) of MTU in dependence on simulation time.

Fig. 13 – Root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) of α sub-unit amino acid residues of MTU.

Fig. 14 – Distance between the flap center and the middle of a straight line connecting Ni atoms in the active center of MTU.

with low amplitude indicating that flap remains in closed state blocking an access to the active center. Recently, similar dynamic behavior of the flap in closed state was observed by Minkara M.S. et al. during the molecular dynamics simulation of *Helicobacter pylori* urease for 400 ns [81].

Taken together, the revealed structural features of 3D model of *M. tuberculosis* urease suggest that the overall structure of the enzyme is stable.

Conclusions

In this study three-dimensional structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease has been predicted by homology modeling. Thorough structure validations by alternative algorithms confirmed good quality of our homology model of *M. tuberculosis* urease. The structural stability of the model and the peculiarities of the dynamic behavior of its flap covering the active center was studied by molecular dynamics simulation of MTU in aqueous solution at 300 K for 60 ns. Analysis of MD trajectory indicate that the enzyme global structure is stable and the flap covering the active center remains in closed state during the simulation time. Predicted three-dimensional structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease can be used in the studies of structure-function relationships of the enzyme, in design of new safe and efficient enzyme inhibitors aimed to struggle with infectious diseases promoted by urease activity.

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HOMOLOGY MODELING AND MOLECULAR DYNAMICS STUDY OF MYCOBACTERIUM TUBERCULOSIS UREASE

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Introduction. *M. tuberculosis* urease (MTU) is an attractive target for chemotherapeutic intervention in

tuberculosis by designing new safe and efficient enzyme inhibitors. A prerequisite for designing such inhibitors is an understanding of urease's three-dimensional (3D) structure organization. 3D structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease is unknown. When experimental three-dimensional structure of a protein is not known, homology modeling, the most commonly used computational structure prediction method, is the technique of choice. This paper aimed to build a 3D-structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease by homology modeling and to study its stability by molecular dynamics simulations. **Materials and methods.** To build MTU model, five high-resolution X-ray structures of bacterial ureases with three-subunit composition (2KAU, 5G4H, 4UBP, 4CEU, and 4EPB) have been selected as templates. For each template five stochastic alignments were created and for each alignment, a three-dimensional model was built. Then, each model was energy minimized and the models were ranked by quality Z-score. The MTU model with highest quality estimation amongst 25 potential models was selected. To further improve structure quality the model was refined by short molecular dynamics simulation that resulted in 20 snapshots which were rated according to their energy and the quality Z-score. The best scoring model having minimum energy was chosen as a final homology model of 3D structure for *M. tuberculosis*. The final model of MTU was also validated by using PDBsum and QMEAN servers. These checks confirmed good quality of MTU homology model. **Results and discussion.** Homology model of MTU is a nonamer (homotrimer of heterotrimers, ($\alpha\beta\gamma$)₃) consisting of 2349 residues. In MTU heterotrimer, sub-units α , β , and γ tightly interact with each other at a surface of approximately 3000 Å². Sub-unit α contains the enzyme active site with two Ni atoms coordinated by amino acid residues His347, His349, carbamylated Lys430*, His459, His485, Asp 573, Gly490. Helix-turn-helix motif (residues 524-545) forms a mobile flap that covers the active site and is in closed conformation impeding access to the enzyme active site. The structural stability of MTU model was checked by molecular dynamics simulation in explicit water at 300 K and pH 7.4. During the simulation, root mean square deviations of C α atoms (RMSD C α) and root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) of amino acid residues of MTU were monitored for 60 ns. Also, the distance between the loop that covers the active site and the dinickel center was monitored. Analysis of MD trajectory indicate that the enzyme global structure is stable and the flap covering the active center remains in closed state during the simulation time. **Conclusion.** Predicted three-dimensional structure of *M. tuberculosis* urease can be used in the studies of structure-function relationships of the enzyme, in designing new safe and efficient enzyme inhibitors aimed to struggle with infectious diseases promoted by urease activity.

Key words: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* urease, three-dimensional structure, homology modeling, molecular dynamics simulations